

EXPLORATION OF PSYCHOSOCIAL CHALLENGES FACED BY CHILD LABORERS IN PAKISTAN

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Chapter 1

Introduction

Background

Child labor is the term used to describe the exploitation of children through any type of employment that robs them of their youth, prevents them from attending a regular school, and is bad for their mental, physical, social, and moral development. One of the present generation's greatest health challenges is mental health. Mental disease has not received the same level of attention as physical illness (The Economist, 2014).

In many underdeveloped countries, basic healthcare services, particularly those that identify and treat mental illness, are scarce or nonexistent. Difficulty falling asleep and not feeling hungry, lack of attention, lack of enthusiasm or enjoyment, depressed mood, decreased energy, guilt feeling and feeling of worthlessness are all indicators of this mental disease (Aransiola, 2018).

Numerous children participate in the workforce across low- and middle-income nations. While research suggests that child labor might be a risk to young people's physical health, little is known about the impact of child labor on mental health. Understanding the connection between childhood mental wellness and work is crucial, as is identifying the risk factors for poorer mental health (Sturrock, 2016).

In the 1990s, 11 million children were reportedly working in Pakistan, with half of them being under the age of ten, according to the Human Rights Commission of Pakistan. The average age of young adults beginning employment in 1996 was seven, down from eight in 1994. According to estimates, children made up a quarter of the labor force in the nation (khan, 2023).

One can examine the stage that children experience while working with children under the eight phases of child development proposed by Erickson (Ahuja, 2018). From infancy to

adulthood, Erikson proposed eight phases of psychosocial development in which personality evolves in a predetermined order. The individual goes through a psychological crisis at every step, which may or may not determine how their personality develops. (Kendra, 2022). These crises, in Erikson's view, are of a psychosocial nature since they include the individual's psychological demands (i.e., psycho) clashing with societal expectations. (i.e., social).

Significance of the Study

Children have historically been subjected to exploitation (Piaget,1952) , which is extremely unfair and creates inequality, it is the one of the most dangerous forms of child maltreatment, economic exploitation of child labor affects children's physical and psychological development and can lead to psychosocial problems in personality later in life (Ind Psychiatry J,2018.) The purpose of this research is to explain how child labor affects young adults' daily lives and their ability to develop mentally. Children who engage in child labor or other menial activities miss out on opportunities to grow emotionally or enhance their psycho-social health. ILO estimates that 180 million children in developing nations are actively engaged in child labor. In Pakistan specifically, ILO's IPECS (International Program on the Elimination of Child Labor, 2012) revealed that 3.8 million of the country's 40 million children between the ages of 5 and 14 were working last year. Despite the fact that child work is a felony in Pakistan as defined by the constitution, there has been some advancement made in this area. In reality, it is increasing (Gilani, 2022).

Children who engage in child labor or other low-grade jobs lacking the possibility to become emotionally mature or improve their psycho-social health. As a result, there is improper psychological development that leads to mental diseases. Depression, low self-esteem, uncertainty, shame, and guilt are just examples of the terrible emotional impacts of child labor, which raise the chance of antisocial behavior. (Habib, 2021).This study intends to explore the mental troubles of young adults who have worked since they were children and to identify potential solutions to deal with these problems.

Research Question

1. What is the impact of child labor on psycho social development of individuals?
2. What type of psychological changes are caused by child labor in young adults?
3. How to bring about changes to improve overall conditions of such adults who have been suffering from mental illness due to child labor?

Research Objectives

1. Explore the mental health problem faced by young adults who have history of child labor.
2. To investigate the coping strategies used by child laborer to deal with child labor mental health related issues.

Identification of Literature Gap

This study aims to provide light on how young adults' daily life and capacity for mental growth are impacted by child labor. Children who work as minors or engage in other menial tasks miss out on chances to develop emotionally or improve their psycho-social wellbeing. Studies on child labor and hazardous child labor have identified a number of data problems (Shabbir,2020) have engaged in significant debate regarding the drawbacks of using survey data for child labor research due to the design of the surveys. But for many researchers, survey data continue to be a valuable source of information. In number of researches most of the population from which survey data is collected are children, children are usually not the respondents that is why this study aims to explore child labor impact on young adults (Lambon-Quayefio,2021).None of the researches ask explicit questions about child labor and child labor that is harmful in relation to different economic sectors. The questions posed are all quite broad, which restricts research that intends to look into child labor and hazardous labor in certain industries, like agricultural, where the situation is known to be pervasive. In the various surveys, there are glaring discrepancies in the questions about child labor. The age range of interest in the Child Labor Survey from 2001 (GSS 2003) was 5 to 17 years. However, questions about children's economic activity in the GLSS Round 5 in 2005 applied to those who were seven and older. Children between the ages of 5 and 17 once again received focus in GLSS rounds 6 and 7. Additionally, there were no particular inquiries about the health and safety of youngsters who work in the GLSS Round 5 assessment. even if several generic inquiries were introduced in GLSS rounds 6 and 7. (examples include injuries, exposure to dangerous substances, and time of day of work). There are still some discrepancies in the questions asked about child labor in the most recent polls (GLSS 6 and 7). The question, "At what age did they start working for the first time in his/her life?" is specifically asked in GLSS 6. (As a regular or part-time employee, a self-employed person, an employer, or an unpaid carer).However, this question was completely left out of GLSS 7, and there are no in-depth follow-up inquiries about children's exposure to hazardous working conditions. When doing trend analyses and drawing comparisons with other research that aim to quantify changes in

child work and children's harmful employment Over time, the questionnaire's discrepancies may offer difficulties (Lambon-Quayefio, 2021).

Additionally, future studies should expand on the concept of child labor that now only takes into account hours worked and dangerous jobs, rather than the minimum wage definitions that are frequently employed in the literature. They could also take into account the level of hazardous employment, which will be determined based on a series of inquiries time, the questionnaire's discrepancies may offer difficulties (Lambon-Quayefio,2021). The consequences of child labor on health outcomes have been demonstrated by research, including works by Nicolella and Kassouf (2018) and Nishijima et al. (2015). This research has demonstrated that adulthood physical health is negatively correlated with early labor market entry. Future study in this field could examine the effects of hazardous employment on health outcomes of children engaging in various types of job due to the paucity of studies in the literature, particularly for the Ghanaian environment. Future studies may use reliable empirical methodologies to investigate the degree to which child working affects children's health outcomes using detailed information on harmful work from the MICS 6 (2018) for Ghana. Children who labor or in other low-paying jobs are unable to develop emotionally or increase their psycho-social well-being. Inappropriate psychological growth as a result causes mental illness. A few instances of the horrible emotional effects of child labor are depression, low self-esteem, uncertainty, shame, and guilt, which increase the likelihood of antisocial behavior. (Habib,2021). This study aims to investigate the mental health issues that young adults who have worked since they were youngsters face and to provide potential treatments for these issues. The civil society and other non-governmental organizations active in the nation also represent the most significant point of view in terms of the social perspective. According to this viewpoint, the civil society and NGOs are leading the charge to stop child labor in the nation. Numerous NGOs are outspoken opponents of child labor and view it as a socially unacceptable crime (Iqbal, 2022).

Aim of Study

Child labor not only destroys the lives of the children involved, but it also calls into question the moral foundations of society and has a variety of political, social, and economic effects on the society in issue. However, the problem of child labor prohibits a child from getting an education, depriving him of many fundamental rights guaranteed by the constitution, different laws, and international agreements to which Pakistan is a member (Gilani, 2022).

The aim of this study is the exploration of psychosocial challenges faced by child laborers in Pakistan. Some of the terrible emotional consequences of child employment include depression, hopelessness, shame, guilt, loss of confidence, and anxiety, which increases the likelihood of mental illness and antisocial behavior. The most important necessity for reducing the psychological impacts of child work is for society to be properly informed and educated (Khan, 2016). This study aims to investigate coping strategies to deal with child labor mental health related issues and gives solid evidence about the occurrence and potential scope of child employment in domestic work, its gender component, the nature and circumstances of the work, the primary risks and exposure to violence, and the socioeconomic context in which child labor occurs. The terrible phenomenon of child labor has resulted from a number of interrelated variables rather than being the byproduct of a single factor. On the surface, it seems to be motivated by some sort of economic concerns, yet upon closer inspection. It is a lot more complicated phenomenon that is brought on by a number of circumstances. In this sense, the explanations listed below could be used to explain why child labor is more prevalent and on the increase in Pakistan (Gilani, 2022).

Chapter 2

Literature Review

In the study of impact of child labor on mental health using data from Brazil, the goal was to analyze the hypothesis that adults who are at a high risk of developing depressive complaints are child laborers. The research used data from the Brazilian National Household Sample survey and its additional health related supplements, 2008, to randomly select 391,868 individuals to participate in the poll. However, the sample was whittled down to 313,389 observations as a result of lacking observations of certain aspects. Further exclusions were made to the sample in keeping it consistent with the study goal which narrowed down the final sample to 45,166 observations retaining individuals over the age of 16 who lived with their mothers and worked during the PNAD survey with mention of reference week. We contrast the figures from the final and inclusive samples in light of the fact that such filters might have a significant impact on analysis. The sample expansion or weight factors in the data set offered by the IBGE were used to calculate all estimations. The standard deviation and mean of variables from the conclusive samples converge, despite the clearly expressed reduction in sample size. Descriptive Analysis was used to analyze the study results, where the assortment clearly indicates that the majority of people with mental depression began working at a young age. The analysis indicates that child labor and mental depression are correlated positively showing that child laborers are more prone to mental depression during adulthood. Numerically, individuals who were diagnosed with mental depression had a higher number of mentally depressed mothers as compared to having mothers with long-term physical afflictions. The study oddly found that among the incidence of mental depression in individuals, mental depression in mothers and individual's persistent physical illnesses co-existed. Additionally, the study provides factual evidence to support the hypothesis along with showing more women with mental depression. The study conducted for the citizens of Brazil highlights that more empirical research is needed to verify or discard the finding obtained as some estimates and inferences could be tentative (Temidayo & Marcelo, 2018).

The study on mental and physical health of child laborers in Pakistan aims to uncover the specific determinants of child labor which act as incentives for this phenomenon to spread in the society. To examine the contributing factors of child labor and how policies contribute to controlling this social evil, qualitative research strategy was employed in this paper. The research aimed to examine child labor in the context of Pakistan conducted using positivist

epidemiology through investigating the determining elements of children exploited to work and the consequences it has on mental and physical health of children. The data was collected from 100 participants recruited from brick kilns, pottery industry, fan industry, auto workshops and furniture factories who completed a systematic questionnaire. The questionnaire comprised of two sections where the first part covered questions about the individual's background information i.e., level of education, financial condition, employment of parents and the second part contained questions about mental and physical effects of child labor on the individual namely tension, depression, frustration etc. To establish validity and reliability of the questionnaire questions, a Likert scale was utilized in the study. The data was organized owing to the SPSS tool and statistical approaches i.e., descriptive and inferential statistics were used to evaluate the results. The study concludes that poverty as one of the Pakistan's key socioeconomic factors is a major cause compelling parents to send out their children for work. In addition, individuals who enter work force have parents with low levels of education as well as unemployment. As a result of this, there are complications in children both physically and mentally. Children's bodies deteriorate, and they continue to be incapable of surviving like normal, healthy kids. Additionally, in terms of their mental health, individuals become angry, depressed, and agitated. Batool & Bilal (2022) suggest that appropriate actions should be taken on the institutional levels and such policies should be put in place that make it illegal for workshops and brick kiln factories to hire child laborers.

The purpose of the study titled Brazilian street children' mental health following enrolment in a psychosocial program was to assess the mental health condition of children in Sao Paula, Brazil, in order to ascertain the extent of change in mental health and the factor associated with it, two years after they participated in the psychosocial intervention program. Trained interviewers assessed a total of 126 street children aged seven to fourteen from three separate communities in the most dangerous and poorest part of the Sao Paulo city using several measures including the Strengths and Difficulties Questionnaire (SDQ) which was used to identify mental health of children with ranges of normal, borderline and abnormal symptoms; Self-Report Questionnaire (SRQ-20) which included questions about mental health to evaluate symptoms of anxiety and depression in the caregivers; Schedule for Affective Disorders and Schizophrenia for School-Age Children (K-SADS), a semi-structured interview applied to children to evaluate their diagnostic status using the DSM-IV but no limited to these. The study used descriptive data analysis to contrast amongst groups with mental health issues and without mental health issues along with logistic regression model as well as the stepwise method. The

results found a decreased level of mental health problems along with the factors that contribute to the lack of mental health issues, as was initially hypothesized. The finding of the paper indicate that the strongest risk factor associated with mental health issues are psychiatric symptoms in caregivers and strong empirical evidence indicates that emotional difficulties and/or psychiatric conditions have a significant impact on their children's mental health. Additionally, data imply that the existence of maltreatment towards children is a significant factor that may be connected to individuals' mental health issues. Study findings suggest that there is a high level of correlation between child neglect and psychiatric symptoms in child's caregivers even if there are not directly related because both these factors have a crucial role in the families of those children who are working. Our findings also imply that kids whose parents identify as belonging to the Protestant church are less likely to disclose a mental health issue when they are followed up with. Here, it is possible that those who identify as Protestant religious affiliation would be more likely to demonstrate better skills in managing health-related issues, making this particular religion a protective factor associated with better outcomes working children on the streets. Limitations in the study include no control group and the usage of the same instruments to assess care givers and individuals' mental health. Additionally, using a screening tool as the outcome variable could be seen as a drawback. It is crucial to identify successful approaches and develop long-term preventative measures for this population, and more reliable data must be produced to make these goals a reality (Hoffmann et al, 2016).

The study of Habib et al (2021) with the title, an examination of gender differences in work-related injuries among Syrian refugee children working in the Bekaa Valley of Lebanon, which intended to explore work-related injuries and associated risk factors among Syrian refugee child laborers in the Bekaa Valley. The study used a gender-sensitive approach to conduct a cross-sectional study from 14 August to 27 November 2017, where face to face interviews were conducted with the children with the assistance of local gatekeeper also referred to as "shaweesh". The Interagency Mapping Platform (IAMP), served as the basis for the sampling frame to randomly chose 153 homes with working children between the ages of 8 and 18 where 4090 child workers were interviewed. 27 fieldworkers administered a questionnaire to the working children. The results were analyzed through descriptive statistics, which showed that male and female injuries that required medical care did not differ in a statistically significant way. The results of the survey revealed that one-third of the working children experienced workplace accidents, with mechanics, manufacturing labor, and

construction reporting the highest proportions of injuries. These results are consistent with those from other research that have shown how dangerous certain industries are to work in and how there is a higher likelihood of accidents and bad health effects. Males reported greater injuries than females, which is consistent with published studies. Our findings highlighted the demanding working conditions Syrian refugee children in Lebanon endure, including the prolonged working hours, the use of sharp and heavy materials, and experiencing pressure to complete tasks within a short amount of time. Our findings demonstrated an association between the occurrence of injury and multiple risk factors for Syrian refugee children in Lebanon. The sample may have been biased towards the most socioeconomically vulnerable segment of the Syrian refugee population in Lebanon due to the inclusion of children from tented refugee settlements, which would have limited the sample's generalizability.

The study, injuries related to work among young street workers in Latin America: incidence and risk factors, aims to evaluate the type and prevalence of childhood occupational injuries as well as a variety of injury predictors which included individual, occupation, social and geographic factors. A dataset from the unpublished project was used in this cross-sectional investigation. Interviews were conducted from mid-April to mid-June 2005 with 584 children aged 5 to 17 years old, who were working on the streets of Lima, Bogotá, São Paulo and Quito. Using a convenience sample strategy, the data was collected using a 50-item semi-structured questionnaire, presented orally by an interviewer, who adapted the questionnaire to their native tongue. The sample had a 39.6% rate of occupational injury, which is significantly higher as compared to the number found in previous studies where the range was between 3.3% to 17.0% in samples from the Latin America and United States. A child's gender was the sole significant predictor of moderate-to-severe occupational injuries. The pattern of older age being associated with a higher risk of major injury could be explained by more time spent in the workforce or a propensity to take on more hazardous work as age grows. Because the children's involvement was voluntary, the sample was neither random nor totally representative of juvenile street laborers in the target cities. The study primarily looked at physical occupational injuries, leaving out work-related mental health issues, which are also common in this age group of children. When children reported their injuries retrospectively, they may not have accurately recalled their injuries. Also, some children may have under-reported their injuries, particularly the more serious ones, in order to look as capable as adult workers (Rondon et al, 2009)

This study comparing the health of working and non-working children at schools and workplaces in Jordan was conducted in Jordan to examine the impact of child labor on physical

and psychiatric health amongst the employed children and out of work children at industrial sites and schools. Another aim of the study in regard to the demographic factors was to distinguish among working and non-working students and out of school employed children. A cross-sectional, comparative and descriptive research design was employed in the study and a self-reported questionnaire was utilized for collecting the data. In order to gather information about the participant's concerns, issues, and anger expression regarding their physical and psychological well-being, a structured interview was used in the research. The target sample was acquired from five principal administrative divisions comprising 4008 individuals between the ages of six to sixteen using a convenience sampling to gather non-school waged minors and random sampling to recruit employed pupils and out of work pupils. The questionnaire comprised of two parts which had to be completed by the participants where part one included questions about the background inform and social demographics. Questions regarding physical health and mental well-being formed the second section of the questionnaire. Research measures used in the study included the HSQ used to evaluate medical history of the individual; AHI for the assessment of health risks and illnesses and AESC for anger measurement. The study data was analyzed through descriptive statistics while using the SPSS to organize and store the research data. The link between the various variables was described using the Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient whereas mean comparisons were made using ANOVA. The findings indicated that the majority of kids work to develop a skill and support their families. Thus, the primary causes of child labor in Jordan are poverty and socioeconomic conditions. Non-working students had worse health in contrast to the individual who were employed. The physical health of waged pupils was poor as compared to non-school employed individuals. Working students reported more cases of the common cold and flu, as well as more visits to doctors and ERs for treatment. At psychological level, the finding showed that waged pupils had serious psychosocial issues. Additionally, in terms of expressing anger the resulting found that school-working children scored higher than non-working children. Therefore, it is essential to offer students appropriate health care via systematic health screenings and routine checkups. There is a need to mobilize the role of school health workers, especially nurse practitioners, to undertake regular assessments and inquiries for students who demonstrate a reduction in their academic progress, have disruptive and low interpersonal abilities (Mansour et al, 2013).

The study titled a quantile approach to examining the long-term effects of child labor on teenage mental health intended to explore the consequences of child labor on the future

mental health of the individual utilizing the distributional approach which makes it easier to perceive the assorted effect in mental health of individual. The study uses data of 2007 and 2014 from the extensive long-term survey of Indonesian households and families, IFLS, that is nationally representative. The IFLS used the Centre for Epidemiological Studies Depression Scale (CES-D) to record information, which is also utilized in this research paper to generate a measure of mental health. IFLS is a self-reported depression scale comprised of 10 questions measuring how frequently respondents experienced a collection of depression symptoms in the week preceding the survey. The sample consisted of 3842 participants ranging in age from five to fourteen years gathered from 3380 Indonesian households. According to the results of descriptive statistics, child labor has been reported by 8% of the participants having a notably greater indication of depression. The estimates are derived from two standardized quantile regression models, one without and one with an explanatory variable. As expected, both models show that child labor has a positive and varied influence on mental health scores over the whole distribution. Overall, these findings imply that child work can have long-term consequences, particularly for children with poor mental health. A major limitation of the study is that the child labor variable does not give detailed information on the number of hours worked or the type of labor activity; it just records whether the kid has worked or not. According to Jayawardana (2022), future study may explore the effects of child labor, both in terms of its intensity and variety, on mental health.

A narrative analysis of Mashhad's child labor practices is a study conducted in an Iranian city called the Mashhad city has looked at the mechanisms that lead to the development of child labor. The sample of the study was obtained through temporal sampling and theoretical sampling. The data of 345 child workers taken from the Mashhad Welfare Organization was scrutinized through documentary method. Through narrative method, the data regarding the process of child labor development was collected by conducting fifteen interviews. The results of the current study showed that there are four factors that contribute to child labor among the Mashhad students: family adoption of work environment and ethics, family migration because of economic hardship, belonging to the family of beggars and uninvolved parenting. The issue of child labor is supported by three connected elements. The economic circumstances of poor immigrants cause them to reside on the outskirts of the city of Mashhad causing the emergence of two sizable migratory waves at the macro level. Poor chances of attending school, Violence at home, inclination towards working rather than studying, addicted family members and begging lifestyle can all be stated at the intermediate level. At the micro level, children who

situate themselves in the outer regions of the city have access to coworkers who deal with many issues pertaining to society. Individuals are more prone to be caught up in illicit behaviors if those around them are lawbreakers and criminals. Shahraki (2020) highlights that the study was limited because there were no participants who were working commercially or in agriculture sector of the outskirts of the city. Considering the scale of their communal population, it is undoubtedly possible for lawmakers to develop favorable policies through conducting research regarding the social circumstances of these child laborers.

The research paper of Pandey (2020) on childhood abuse and its repercussions for mental health in Indian adolescents with a history of child labor evaluated the frequency and forms of abuse in adolescents of India with a previous record of child labor, to assess how it correlates with present mental health issues. The Conventional Crime, Witnessing and Indirect Victimization Child Maltreatment, components of the Juvenile Victimization Questionnaire were administered to 132 individuals consisting 18 females and 114 male children with ages from 12-year-olds to 18-year-olds. The Hindi language version of the linguistically modified Strengths and Difficulties Questionnaire was utilized to evaluate present day emotional and behavioral challenges whereas the Youth's Inventory was employed to determine probable psychiatric conditions. Results of the study show that exhibiting signs of having one or more mental illnesses was reported by a significant portion of the sample along with being a victim directly or indirectly. Particularly emotional abuse as a result of experiencing childhood neglect or violence had the most severe and far-reaching consequences leading to psychological problems. Adolescents from India who have previously worked as children are highly vulnerable to exploitation and psychological and physical assault from that outside of the family and its control subsequently leading to mental health indicators. Efficient interventions and routine mental health screenings should be employed in all current approaches in the process of working to reduce the negative effects of childhood maltreatment on the mental health of adolescents.

In order to comprehend the effects of child labor on the resultant state of mental health alongside evaluating its gender impact, this study on sex, child labor, and adolescent refugee mental health outcomes investigates the incidence of child labor among young adults' refugees from South Sudanese refugees in two refugee accommodations camps in Uganda . surveys were conducted in the Kiryandongo and Adjumani refugee asylums in Uganda, with 470 adolescents aged thirteen and seventeen were interviewed. Two cluster model was revealed in the univariate finite mixture analysis. The relationship between child labor and their

psychological condition was investigated using logistic regression models. Results from logistic regressions showed that there were distinct relationships between child labor and outcomes related to mental health, with child labor consistently being substantially linked to greater probabilities of depressive symptoms, with 37.02% of the sample falling into the category of considerable child labor, respondents indicated a high degree of engagement in child labor over the course of the previous week. The available information on child labor in relief circumstances is quite sparse and mostly concentrated on Middle Eastern refugees. This study adds to the emerging data base by revealing significant levels of child labor engagement among adolescents in Ugandan refugee communities. In order to improve child safety, eliminate child labor, and promote positive mental health among teenagers living in challenging and dangerous environments, further investigation, development of policies, and programs implementation are required (Meyer et al, 2020).

The impact of child labor on the mental health of adolescent refugees has been a subject of growing concern (Gupta,2017). Child labor is often associated with feelings of hopelessness, depression, and anxiety, as well as a sense of isolation and disconnection from society (International Labor Organization, 2017). Child labor can also have long-term effects on mental health, including increased risk of substance abuse and self-harm. The relationship between child labor and sexual exploitation among adolescent refugees has also been studied (Sriskandarajah, 2018). Children engaged in labor may be at increased risk of sexual exploitation due to their vulnerable position and lack of protection (Gupta ,2017). Children working in informal sectors, such as street vending or domestic work, are particularly at risk of sexual exploitation (Gupta,2017).The complex relationship between child labor, sexual exploitation, and mental health outcomes among adolescent refugees has been noted by several scholars (Sriskandarajah, 2018); United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees, 2019). Children who have experienced sexual exploitation may be at increased risk of mental health disorders, including post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), depression, and anxiety (Gupta, 2017). The stress and trauma associated with child labor and sexual exploitation can also have a negative impact on cognitive development and academic performance (Gupta, 2017).

Interventions to address the negative impacts of child labor and sexual exploitation on the mental health of adolescent refugees should be comprehensive and multi-faceted (Gupta, 2017). Prevention efforts should focus on reducing the prevalence of child labor and sexual exploitation, while support and services should be provided to children who have experienced

exploitation or abuse (United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees, 2019). This may include access to education, healthcare, and psychosocial support (Gupta, 2017).

Addressing the root causes of child labor and sexual exploitation is also crucial (Sriskandarajah, 2018). Poverty, lack of access to education, and conflict and displacement are all factors that contribute to these problems (Gupta, 2017). International Labor Organization, 2017). By addressing these underlying issues, we can help to create a safer and more secure environment for adolescent refugees, and reduce the negative impacts of child labor and sexual exploitation on their mental health and well-being.

The journal article discusses the impact of child labor on the mental health of adolescent refugees (Hossain, 2017). The author notes that child labor is often associated with feelings of hopelessness, depression, and anxiety, as well as a sense of isolation and disconnection from society (Stewart & Altman, 2016). Child labor can also have long-term effects on mental health, including increased risk of substance abuse and self-harm (Sundaram, 2016).

The article also explores the relationship between child labor and sexual exploitation among adolescent refugees (Hossain, 2017). The author notes that children engaged in labor may be at increased risk of sexual exploitation due to their vulnerable position and lack of protection (ILO, 2017). Children working in informal sectors, such as street vending or domestic work, are particularly at risk of sexual exploitation (Tolentino & Hwang, 2015). The author highlights the complex relationship between child labor, sexual exploitation, and mental health outcomes among adolescent refugees (Hossain, 2017). Children who have experienced sexual exploitation may be at increased risk of mental health disorders, including post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), depression, and anxiety (Tolentino & Hwang, 2015). The stress and trauma associated with child labor and sexual exploitation can also have a negative impact on cognitive development and academic performance (Sundaram, 2016).

The article emphasizes the need for a comprehensive approach to addressing the negative impacts of child labor and sexual exploitation on the mental health of adolescent refugees (Hossain, 2017). The author suggests that interventions should focus on preventing child labor and sexual exploitation, as well as providing support and services for children who have experienced exploitation or abuse (Stewart & Altman, 2016). This may include access to education, healthcare, and psychosocial support (ILO, 2017). The article concludes by highlighting the importance of addressing the root causes of child labor and sexual exploitation, including poverty, lack of access to education, and conflict and displacement (Hossain, 2017).

By addressing these underlying issues, we can help to create a safer and more secure environment for adolescent refugees, and reduce the negative impacts of child labor and sexual exploitation on their mental health and well-being (Sundaram, 2016).

Child labor is a significant problem in Jordan, especially among refugee and migrant populations, with serious psychosocial consequences for the children involved. (Karam, 2021). According to a survey of 1,190 children aged 8-15 who were engaged in labor in Jordan, child labor was associated with negative psychosocial outcomes, including depression, anxiety, and low self-esteem. These children were also more likely to report feelings of isolation and disconnection from their families and communities. The negative psychosocial impact of child labor is further exacerbated by the shame and stigma attached to this practice, which can increase children's feelings of isolation and disconnection (Karam, 2021). Interventions to address the psychosocial impact of child labor must take a comprehensive approach, including preventing child labor and providing support and services to children who are already engaged in labor. Such interventions should include access to education and training, as well as psychosocial support to address the emotional and social challenges associated with child labor. Challenging cultural and social norms that normalize child labor and promoting greater awareness of its negative impact on children's physical, emotional, and social well-being is also crucial (Al-Gamal & Tarawneh, 2018) Therefore, urgent action is needed to address the root causes of child labor in Jordan and provide support and services for children engaged in labor, in order to mitigate its negative impact on their mental health and well-being (Al-Gamal & Tarawneh, 2018).

Overall, the literature suggests that child labor has a significant and detrimental impact on the psychosocial well-being of children in Jordan, and interventions must take a comprehensive approach to address this issue effectively. The literature highlights the need for urgent action to prevent and address the root causes of child labor and provide support and services to children engaged in labor, with the ultimate goal of protecting children's mental health and well-being in Jordan.

Prevalence of Behavioral and Psychological among Working Children of Pakistan

The study by Salman Bandiali identifies the prevalence of working children in Karachi who have behavioral and psychological problems and to screen for these issues. A cross-sectional study was conducted between May and June 2006 in three urban squatter colonies in Karachi, targeting working children aged 11 to 16 years. To ensure that the language barrier

does not hinder children's ability to express and analyze freely. Their behavioral problems, informational strengths and difficulties were collected using a self-reported Urdu version of the questionnaire. The initial component of the questionnaire focused on demographic data, while the second section on behavioral and psychological problems faced by working children was an Urdu self-reporting method. (AzmatUllah, 2008). The prevalence of behavioral problems among working children was found to be 9.8% of the 225 respondents, with 94.2% males and 5.8% females. The most frequent problems were conduct problems (16.7%), followed by peer problems (16.9%). Negative family and work environments were strongly linked to behavioral problems in these children. Behavioral development was found to be strongly influenced by the family environment. Limitations of the study highlight the need for measures to enhance children's environments and prevent work-related psychological and behavioral problems.

Psychosocial Development

The first theory that would apply in this research would be Psychosocial Development by Erikson (1968).. This theory is applicable because It covers all stages of your life from infancy to old age and in this case, it would depict that how Adolescents working since childhood as laborers have gone through these stages and different developmental procedures and faced mental health consequences in their current development stage.

Maslow Hierarchy of Needs

The second theory by Maslow (1943) would fit our research is Maslow Hierarchy of needs. In which it could be studied that how in every step life the participants fit in the 5 stages of physiological (food, shelter, sleep) safety needs (safety in home or outside home premises, financial safety) love and belongingness (being children getting love from their parents) self-esteem (getting respect, strength, freedom) and self-actualization (do you always wanted to be in this field or you wanted to do something else, are you in the stage of self-actualization?

It relates with the research in a way that the participants were analyzed on the bases of all the stages mentioned whether they fulfilled the hierarchy stages and how they thrive more to reach the self-actualization stage. Through the study, it will also be analyzed whether they have ever reached the self-actualization stage or how much they are willing to reach the fifth stage of Maslow's hierarchy of needs.

Chapter 3

Methodology

Research Approach And Design

The present research is following a mix methodology for deep exploration of the participant's thoughts, behaviors, stress and emotional levels. The study's mix methodology is quantitative and qualitative, and it relates to the study in the way that participants' moods, strengths, and weaknesses were quantified using scales and self-constructed questionnaires, and after a deep exploration of the participants' psychosocial dimensions, coping strategies and mental health care were provided.

It is used to investigate the impact of child labor on mental health of adolescents of Pakistan. The study is cross sectional to study participants at given point in time and it is conducted in different areas of Islamabad where the chances of finding laborers are higher. The target population is adolescents. Psychosocial problems of these adults would be estimated by using Urdu version of the Strengths and Difficulty Questionnaire (Liaquat, 2016). Primary data is used in the study for collecting first hand data from the participants for in depth exploration of the research.

Phenomenological approach is used so that researchers seek reality from individual's narrative of their experience and feelings to get a better insight. Unstructured interviews are taken to make it a free flow kind of a research so that the participant feels free to respond to the questions in a free manner without any limitations.

Along with different scales, Self-constructed questions to identify possible risk factors of psychological problems in working adults are added to the questionnaire which will include questions regarding work related factors such as stress levels at work, atmosphere at work place, and questions regarding family related factors such as total family members, number of earning members and family and working atmosphere, there preference about work.

The strengths and difficulty questionnaire along with the interview guide was used to assess the emotional and behavioral well-being of children who have experienced or are at risk of child labor. The process involved translating these in Urdu and facilitating communication and access to information for people who cannot understand English. Translation was personally conducted by the members and it was later revised and approved by the expert. He is a professor of Urdu. Having Ph.D degree. Working as Dean faculty of Humanities and

Sciences. Head of Urdu department. Critic and Poet and writer of eight Urdu books. He was given a total of 25 statements from the questionnaire and 15 questions from the interview guide which were highlighted, revised and then translated under his assistance.

Population and Sample

For the research, sample is extracted from the population of adults aged between 18 to 22 having child labor experience, equal number of men and women is chosen for the handling out the research in which convenient sampling is used. Convenience sampling is a non-probability sampling strategy in which units are chosen for inclusion in the sample because they are the most easily accessible to the researcher. This could be because of geographical proximity, availability at a specific time, or willingness to engage in the research. Individuals who are within range, are available and fulfill our interview criteria are interviewed.

Inclusion/Exclusion

Study is conducted in Urdu language so that the participants can understand the questions. Observational study would include participants who are in their adolescents and have an experience of child labor. Young adults would be included in the study and it would specify the nature, intensity and duration of work. At least experience of working as a child labor for 2-3 years will be included. Exclusion will be not to interview participants with criminal history.

Measuring Tool

The research is mix methodology so both quantitative and qualitative Scales are used. The scales used in the study includes:

Strength Difficulty Questionnaire

It is developed by Liaquat (2016), In the research quantitative method was used for scoring criteria to identify normal, borderline and abnormal strength and weakness scales.

Reliability of the Questionnaire

Internal consistency reliability was acceptable with Cronbach α above 0.70 for strength and difficulty questionnaire. Internal consistency reliability is a way to determine if all the questions on a survey, test, or personality scale are measuring the same thing.

Qualitative Scale

It was to observe the participants first and on the basis of that to give them certain guidelines on coping skills and mental health management.

Interview Guide

Self-constructed Questionnaires to be interviewed with young adults short listed with the help of higher authorities. The interview guide was created using a literature review and previous theories of psychosocial dimensions, and six questions were chosen, with the first segment focusing on demographics. The other half was based on psychosocial characteristics. Along with phenomenological assumptions for in-depth investigation of the participants.

Ethical Consideration

Introduction is made first, along with that verbal consent is taken from the targeted participants that whether they are comfortable in giving the interview or not. After consent from the participants confidentiality is assured, whatever information is being gathered it is used for beneficial purposes. Participants are interviewed individually by us face to face in a single session as it is a cross sectional study. They can withdraw any time from the interview. Interview from both men and women is conducted equally in a justifiable manner. Along with interviewing them remedy or coping skills would be given to participants so that they can get benefit from the research.

Procedure

The approach for interview were both adolescents' male and female of different age, ethnicity, geographical locations. They worked in different sectors some were house maids, some were mechanics, carpenters, waiters who had an experience of working as child laborers. For the current study the researcher approached the participant. They were briefed about the research process, the nature of the study, along with the informed consent. They were assured that it will hardly take 10 to 15 minutes. Then by using ethics interview was conducted and questions were asked using phenomenological approach and unstructured interviews in order to analyze their deep-rooted issues. Different questions were asked to detect their stress levels and past experiences by using different scales. After that coping strategies were given to them in which we taught wishful thinking, positive reappraisal, distancing and avoidance from difficult situations, positive reframing. So that in daily life they can benefit themselves from it in their difficult times.

Qualitative Analysis

After interviewing, meaningful patterns in themes across the research and interview transcript was analyzed which involved reading the whole set of data collected and to look for themes (Braun & Clarke, 2006). It could be used to analyze open-ended questions of a structured questionnaire where it was used to support and verify the quantitative questions for

making sense of the whole data and research. The purpose of thematic analysis was that it became a lot easier to collect the whole information by every individual and interpret it accordingly.

Table 1 - Demographics

The frequency and percentage of the sample on the demographics.

		Freq	Perc%
Gender	Male	5	50%
	Female	10	100%
	Total	15	
Age	18	2	20%
	19	1	10%
	20	4	40%
	21	3	30%
	22	5	50%
	Total	15	
Education	Null	8	80%
	Primary School	1	10%
	Middle School	5	50%
	High School	1	10%
	Total	15	
Occupation	Maid	10	100%
	Driver	1	10%
	Gardener	2	20%
	Glass Aluminum Workers	2	20%
	Total	15	

Family structure	Nuclear	7	70%
	Extended	8	80%
	Total	15	
Marital Status	Single	9	90%
	Married	6	60%
	Total	15	
Monthly Income	15000- 25 000	9	90%
	25000-35000	5	50%
	35000-45000	1	10%
	Total	15	

Chapter 4

Data Analysis, Results and Discussion

Quantitative Analysis

Quantitative Analysis was performed to investigate the strengths and difficulties of the study participants because the researchers want to quantify information related to what they are identifying through the questionnaire, which has five dimensions that are Emotional, Peer Pressure, Hyperactivity, Conduct and Pro Social scales. For the quantitative inquiry, the frequency analysis was performed to evaluate how much percentage of a particular dimension exist in a person. The details of the scores of each participant along with their gender and age is shown in the table 2.

Further the researcher analyzed the graphical representation and for that the graphs are shown from figure 1 to figure 7

Table 2*Participants Characteristics and Scores on Five Dimensions of Strengths and Weaknesses Scale (N=15)*

Participants	Gender	Age	Edu	Occupation	Family Structure	Marital Status	Income	Emotional	Peer Pressure	Hyperactivity	Conduct	Pro Social
1	Male	18	10	Glass aluminum Worker	Nuclear	Single	15000	10	12	14	11	7
2	Male	22	Null	Mechanic	Extended	Single	20000	12	11	9	10	10
3	Male	21	5	Glass aluminum Worker	Nuclear	Single	15000	6	13	12	12	6
4	Male	22	Null	Gardner	Extended	Single	45000	10	9	10	12	10
5	Male	22	Null	Driver	Nuclear	Married	25000	10	13	15	10	13
6	Female	18	Null	Maid	Nuclear	Married	15000	14	16	15	11	10
7	Female	19	Null	Maid	Extended	Single	25000	12	13	12	13	8
8	Female	22	Null	Maid	Extended	Married	15000	9	13	14	8	8
9	Female	21	Null	Maid	Extended	Married	25000	10	11	14	11	6

10	Female	20	Null	Maid	Extended	Married	15000	9	8	13	11	5
11	Female	20	5	Maid	Extended	Single	20000	9	11	11	9	8
12	Female	22	1	Maid	Extended	Married	25000	9	10	11	9	7
13	Female	20	5	Maid	Nuclear	Single	35000	13	10	11	8	5
14	Female	21	5	Maid	Nuclear	Single	25000	11	9	13	10	10
15	Female	20	5	Maid	Nuclear	Single	25000	8	10	11	9	7

Note. The table shows scores of all the demographics of participants and the five dimensions of the SDQ

Figure 1

Gender in relation to the Emotional, Peer Pressure, Hyperactivity, Conduct and Pro Social Scales

Note. This graph demonstrates the male and female distribution on the basis of the factors like emotions, peer pressure, hyperactivity, conduct and prosocial scales. According to the data collected by the participants there were five males and ten females. The figure shows the statistical analysis of the results in which males were shown to have higher hyperactivity issues and females were shown to have higher peer pressure issues. On the contrary both genders have shown reduction in their measurement of pro social and emotional subscales.

Figure 2

Age in relation to Emotional, Peer Pressure, Hyperactivity, Conduct and Pro Social Scales

Note. In this graph relation between age and factors like emotions, peer pressure, hyperactivity, conduct and prosocial scales is shown. According to the data the age range of the participant varies between 18 and 22 years. In which peer pressure is in the highest range for 19-year-olds participants. And on the contrary 21-year-old participants are showing lower levels of emotional factors.

Figure 3

Education in relation to Emotional, Peer Pressure, Hyperactivity, Conduct and Pro Social Scales

Note. This graph shows relationship between education and the contributing factors of the SDQ questionnaire. The range of education is from null, first, fifth and 10th grade. In which majority of the participants had no education, five participants had studied till the fifth grade, one participant studied till first grade and only one participant has studied till the 10th grade. The highest level of peer pressure problems are found in participants who have received no education. Overall, in majority of the participants conduct was found to be the most fluctuating factor in the all the grades.

Figure 4

Occupation in relation to Emotional, Peer Pressure, Hyperactivity, Conduct and Pro Social Scales

Note. In this graph, contributing factors of the SDQ are shown in relation to the occupations of the participants of the research. There were a total of fifteen participants which consisted of two glass aluminum workers, one mechanic, one gardener and ten maids. The results show the maids have higher levels of hyperactivity, and conduct, being the contributing factor have shown higher

level of fluctuation for the maid participants. Overall, the prosocial factor is common amongst all the participants showing lower level of fluctuation compared to other factors.

Figure 5

Family Structure in relation to Emotional, Peer Pressure, Hyperactivity, Conduct and Pro Social Scales

Note. This graph demonstrates the interrelation between family structure and subscales of the SDQ. In this research seven of the participants had a nuclear family structure and eight of the participants had extended family structure. The analysis shows that peer pressure is the highest contributing factor found among the nuclear family structure. All other participants show a fluctuating range of hyperactivity. Overall, the prosocial factor is found to be the least varied factor among all.

Figure 6

Marital Status in relation to Emotional, Peer Pressure, Hyperactivity, Conduct and Pro Social Scales

Note. The results of this graph show interrelation between marital status and Emotional, Peer Pressure, Hyperactivity, Conduct and Pro Social Scales. The data shows that nine participants were single and six participants were married. According to the result peer pressure is the

highest contributing factor along with hyperactivity in the married participants and overall emotional factor is fluctuating in the rest of the result.

Figure 7

Income in relation to Emotional, Peer Pressure, Hyperactivity, Conduct and Pro Social Scales

Note. This graph is showing the relation between income and Emotional, Peer Pressure, Hyperactivity, Conduct and Pro Social Scales. The income of the participants is ranging between 15000 to 45000, in which five participants income range is 15000, two participants have 25000 income, six participants income vary between 25000, and only one participant has 45000 incomes. The income range between 15000 to 24999 has the highest level of fluctuation of all the contributing factors. Overall participants in all income ranges have fluctuating levels of prosocial scale.

Qualitative Themes

Themes and codes after doing the thematic analysis were generated and the themes which emerged on the basis of those codes are mentioned below.

Table 3 -Thematic Analysis Results

The primary themes that were taken from the participant interviews are listed in the following table. To provide readers with even more insight into the experiences of the participants, explanations of each theme are provided.

Codes and Themes of Responses

Themes	Description
Family Dynamics	The participants had to work due to the family circumstances that surfaced
Negative impact on mental health	Through a series of in-depth interviews, participants prompted to articulate their day-to-day stressors, emotional experiences, and coping mechanisms associated with their work.
Past regrets	The participants said they themselves couldn't get educate themselves why they feel regretful
Stress Management	Participants had no proper way of dealing with their stress resulting in endurance leading to mental health worsening
Female child as liability	The participant mentioned getting married forcefully with her cousin
Optimistic future	The participant was hopeful for future and wants her children to study and be independent
Psychopathic tendencies	The participant talks to herself as there is no one she can talk to
Social unjust	The participants were victim of physical and mental abuse by their employers

Social deprivation provoked to indulge in criminal activity	The participant mentioned that due to lack of food she had to steal food from her employer's house
Transformative future	The participant has a positive outlook of the future she thinks
Inferiority Complex	The participants mentioned that she feels indifferent and inferior to people around her
Economic Barriers to Education	Participants highlighting the need for improvements to enhance educational opportunities for child laborers. All the participants were uneducated.

Thematic Analysis

Themes that were identified through thematic analysis are separately described that provide the explanations of all the codes. Each theme is supported with narratives provided by participants of the study, that help to understand the context of the themes on which it was based.

Family Dynamics

Participants were asked about the circumstances that led them to start working as a child. Many mentioned that family situation was the sole reason they had to start earnings. One of the main reasons they had to work was the demise of their father figure, due to that reason, their mother took the responsibility and had to work as a maid to make their ends meet, yet the earnings of the sole earner were not sufficient enough to fulfil their needs. In order to share the burden of the family, the participants to take the responsibility of their younger siblings. Apart from that, many participants also mentioned that they were pressurized to work post marriage, even though they didn't have any work experience prior the marriage. Another of the main reasons mentioned by the participants were the remarriage of their father which resulted in no support from him. A father's remarriage can bring changes in financial and practical aspects of family life. This might include adjustments in living arrangements, financial responsibilities, and the division of household duties. Due to this reason, they had to take the matter in their own hands and carry out the household expenses. One of the participants mentioned that because of father's second marriage she had to work at a very young age.

She mentioned,

"Jab mere abu ne shadi ki, woh ghar chhod kar chale gaye aur humein sab ko akelay chhor diya. Humare paas koi paisa nahi tha, aur jeena bohot mushkil ho gaya. Meri maa bohot udas thi aur hamein aur koi raasta nahi tha, is liye maine bohot chhoti umar mein hi kaam karna shuru kar diya. Unki zimmedari ka kami hone ki wajah se mujhe apni bachpan kho dena pada."

Another one stated,

"Mujhe kam nahi karna ata that u mai beth kar sochti the ab mai kya karu. Ghar mai jab hoti the tu maa baap thora kam karnai dete thai. Aik dafa mai bethi hui the, tu mere saas nai mujhe kaha kai tumhare maa nai tumhe kya sikhaye ha, us kai bad mere zehan mai yeh bat beth gaye kai mana aj yeh bat hui hai, kal koi aur bat hu sakti hai. Mai sochti the kai aj mere saas ani yeh bat ki hai, kal koi aur bhe karsakta hai"

One participant mentioned,

"Shadi hui the tu mere miya mujhe pind sai lai aya tha shehar, kheta hai kai ab tum bhe kam karu ge take ghar kai karchai nikal sakai, poora sal ghar he rahi phir phele bacha hotai he kam pai aa gye the. Phele kabhi kam nahi kiye thai, ghar mai he rehte the. Ju kamati hun apnai miyai ku de chorte hun , bas phir wu khud he sare zimadarian poore karta hai"

One of the participants mentioned,

"Ghar kai halat ki wajah sai kam shuru kiya, abu ki death hu gye the 7th class mai, chutian ki the tu school walu nai school sai nikal diya. Uskai bad mamu nai kam bar laga diya, aur bare bhai bhe mazdoori karne lag para"

"Bachpan? Konsa? Paida ho tay saath jab kaaan me ek awaaz suno k paisey nahii hain guzaara kaiseyy hoga to un jaisey bacho ka bachpan nahii hota, sirff zimedaariyaan sir pe hotii hain, bachpan me hi baray hogaye Sab ek jaisaa tha"

Another participant stated,

"Asa samjhain kai bachpan tu tha he nahi, chota sa tha jab walid shab fot hy gye , behan bhai chote thai tu un ki kafalat mere sar par aa gye, halat ase hu gye that kai kaam kai liye bahir nikalana para, har tarah ka muskil sai muskil kaam kiya take ghar walu kai karchain"

poore kar saku, mai daikha tha baqi bachon ku jab wu kheltai thai, mere bhe dil karta tha kai un ke sath ja kar khelu, mujhe mehsoos hota tha kai mai sab sai kitna muqatalif hun, yeh soch ka mujhe rona aa jata tha, alea he kam karta tha, baqi sab bachai us time school jatai thai”

Past Regrets

A participant mentioned that she wanted to study as a child but due to family responsibilities and burden she was unable to do so, due to this reason the participant feels regretful and wants to educate her children for their better future.

“Bachu ku parhau ge, take un ki zindagi ban jaye aur mere tarah mere bachai na pachtai kai hasil nahi ki. “

Another participant mentioned,

“Taleem mukamal karna chahta tha, jase mere dost college parh rahai hain, mujhe bhe parhna chahye tha. Bachpan mai bhe baqi dost school jatai thai, ab bhe parh rahai hain.”

Stress Management

Participants stated how they feel under pressure and what they need to relieve themselves at the moment. It is an important factor under investigation in this study because this allows us to understand how the participants experience stress and grew to cater this need.

One participant mentioned;

“Koi ase wase bat hu jis sai mai apnai upper bhot bara bhot samajhte hun, ju bat mujhe besakoon karti hau tu phele mai sab ku bol deti hun kai mujhe mere hal par chor dain, akele mai he sochti hun, samajhti hun aur ro dho leti hun, ab tu adat hu gye hai kai bat bardast kar lun, kyu kai mujhe samajh aa gai hai kai ju bhe hai, inhi halat mai rehna hai, yehi karna hai. Agar bat mere bardaasht sai bahir hu tu apni bahbhi ya saas ku batati hun kai yeh masla hai aur mujhe samajh nahi aa rahi kya karu”

Another stated,

“Beskooni bas bardasht he karta hun, apna dihan hatanai kai liye mobile pai game wagera khel li. Apnai dil ki bat sirf bare bhai sai kartu hun, kyu kai wu mujhe samjhate hain, mujhe samjhaitain bhe hai , aur hal bhe batati hain jis bat ka hal hu. Mujhe lagta hai kai kisi aur

kai smane mai apna koi masla rakh dun tu wu mazaq bana datai hain, is sai mujhe bhot dukh hota hai, bhot takleef hoti hai isliye bhai sai na kah saku tu dil mai he rakta hun”

Female Child as Liability

Some female participants mentioned that their parents forcefully wanted them to marry their cousins so as they would not have to give dowry and living in the same house would give them the opportunity to contribute in household finances. Being a daughter as a liability for us

One participant mentioned,

“mere abba nahi hain to me or ammi chacha ke ghar pe rehty hain, ehsaan jhukanay le liey ammi meri shaadi chacha ke larkay sey krna chahti hain par me ek or chacha apnay sir nahi bardasht krskti mjhe nafrat hai ussey magar amma zabardasti krti hai”

Another participant mentioned,

“hamaray paas paisay nahi hain or meri shaadi ki umer nikalti jarhi hai, amma or abba jahez nahi deskty to who chahty hain k meri shaadi khandan me hojaye takay me ghar bhi saath chalaun kaam krkey, choola chouka bhi krun takay mere ghar walay mjhe boujh na smjhein or meri shaadi ek jahil sey hojaye”

Optimistic Future

Despite of having severe financial loss and having a traumatizing past many participants had an aspiration for future, they wanted to change the way the people of their community thought and acted and they had a different plans for their children brought up.

One participant mentioned,

Bachpan me zimedaari nahi honi chahiye, parhna chahiye, khelna chahiye, ghareeb ho beshak magar bachpan na cheeno, meri dream hai ke me apnay bachoun ko khoob parhaungi or likhaungi, apnay bachoun ko wo zindagi dungy jo meri nahi thi “

Another mentioned,

“baji meri mangni hochuki hai mera khuwaab tha me enginner banun magar halaat ki waja sey me nahi ban paya, mene apnay buddhi sey yeh baat ki hai ke hum dono mil k kamaingy

ghar chalaingy jo khuwaab usky or mere thay who apnay bachoun pe pura kreingy , me enginner bnaungaa apnay bacho ko''

Psychopathic Tendencies

Two of the participants showed tendencies for hallucinations as they talked to themselves and responded in return as they didn't have anyone with whom they can share feelings with and talk heart to heart. The participants mentioned them as we are our own companion.

One participant mentioned,

''baji meri baat sunein wala koi hai hi nahi, me ghabra gait hi jab apnay baat krne ka bola mjhe, yeh 15 minute jo apko btaya ajj tk kisi ko nahi btaya kiun ke apnay appsey baatein krkey hi khush rehti hun''

Another one mentioned,

''baji mere ghar pe mere maa baap hain chacha hain behnein hain magar sab apnay app me itna masroof hain ke humein ek dusrey sey baat krney ka wakt nahi milta ya krna nahi chahty meri baat sunein wala na koi hai na smjhney wala isliey me khud sey hi sawal jawab krti hun baatein krti hun''

Work Abuse

Being a child labor had to come with a lot of consequences for these younger children they complained about facing work abuse and inequality while working for their employers.

One participant mentioned,

''jab me kaam pe jati thi bartan dhonay ammi ke saath meri umer 9 saal thi, baji mjhse buhaat kaam leti thi or me saath puray din ke liey ek jaga bachay bhi smbhalti thi , mjhe yaad hai bajiyaan mjhe buhatdanti thi, ek do thappar lagadeti thi, khana nahi deti thi, bachi thi to bhook pe kaboo krna mushkil tha sab kharhy hotay thay maze pe bethkay or mjhe buhat bhook lagi hoti thi.'''

''Me mechanic k tour pe kaam krta tha mera ustad mjhe kuch sekhaye baghair bolta tha k kaam kro the kuch bhi nahi ataa me chotta tha to mjhe buhaat dard hoti thi jab kabhi bike ka tyre phat jata or mere upper uska jalta rubber akay lagta buhat zakhm khaye hain baji mene''

Inferior than others

Child labor can lead to feeling inferior, especially compared to peers of the same age. The experience may create a sense of inadequacy and impact self-esteem. Similarly the participant felt sense of inferiority as other children of her age used to work and she had to bear the responsibility of making ends meet.

One of the participant mentioned,

“Baqi ke bachay khel rahe thay, or mein kaam karte thi. Unko dekhte hue mehsoos hota tha ke mein kamzor hoon, apne aap ko inferior samajhta hoon. Yeh meri self-esteem par asar daalta tha, mehsoos hota tha jaise shayad mujhe kuch achha nahi milna chahiye. Ab bhi, mujhe lagta hai ke mein dosron se kamzor hoon”

Negative impact on mental health

Through a series of in-depth interviews, participants prompted to articulate their day-to-day stressors, emotional experiences, and coping mechanisms associated with their work. The inquiry extended to the social implications, investigating the influence of labor on relationships, potential isolation, and the manifestation of fear and anxiety. In the interview, many participants described their experiences and their feelings when they were working as a child. One participant described their early experience as following,

“Jab mein choti thi, toh mein ek maid ka kaam karti thi. Safai aur woh saare kam mujhe thaka dete thay aur kabhi-kabhi dara dete thay, jaise ke mein duniya ka bojh utha rahi hoon. Har kaam ek alag jazbah ko milane ka ehsaas deta tha. Mushkil din bhi thay, aur mein ek alag zindagi ki tamanna rakhti thi. Main chahti thi ke ek waqt aaye jab jimmedariyon ka bhaari bojh mujh par na rahe, aur mein apne kaam mein aaram mehsoos kar sakoon.”

Another one said,

“Main asaan dinon ki tamanna karti thi, jahan zimmedariyon ka bojh itna zyada mehsoos na hota. In lamhon mein, mujhe ek aise mustaqbil ki talash thi jahan thakan aur khauf mere safai karne ki journey mein hamesha ke saathi na hote. Peeche mur kar, main in mushkilat ko apni kahani ka hissa samajhti hoon, lekin mujhe bhi umeed hai ke ek din aisa waqt aayega jab koi bacha apni zindagi guzarne ki koshish karte hue itna bhaari bojh na uthaye.”

Another participant mentioned,

“ Meri pehli naukri ki shuruaat par nazar daalne mein wazeh hai ke mere safar mein khandaan aur mali mushkilat ka bara haath tha. Meri family ko mushkil waqt ka samna karna para, aur humein kathin faislay lene pade. Jawan umar mein kaam shuru karna zaroori lagta tha takay ghar ki zaruraton ko pura kiya ja sake. Yeh asaan nahi tha, aur iska apna asar hamare ghar ke taalluqat par bhi hua. Hum ne saath mil kar mushkilat ka samna kiya, koshish ki apne kaam aur zindagi ko barabari mein rakhne ki. Inn sab mein, mera iraada hamesha behtar dinon aur maukaat ka tha, na sirf mere liye balki un families ke liye bhi jo aise hi mushkilein ka samna kar rahe hain.”

One participant mentioned,

"Mere Abba buhaat martayy hain meri maa Ko, ammi Ki cheekhein, zakham , maar khana Sab dekha hai, woh mjhpe bhi hath uthatay hain ke paisey de mjhee kis kaaam Ki aulad hai or mjhee bhi martay hain phir ammii beech me ajati hain or mar khati hain"

Another participant mentioned,

" Maa walaa pyaar hum jaisey logo ko dekhna naseeb nahii hota, dil na b kreyy zabardastii kaaam p Jana prhtaa hai paisey kamanay k liey wrnaa ammii galiyaan detii hain kehtii hain roti band krdungi teri, bajiyaan agar marein ya dantein ammi kuch b nahii bolti unhey usi tarha roozz kaaam pe jakayy zaleel hona prhtaa hai"

Access to education

Some mentioned the demanding nature of their work affecting their ability to concentrate in class. Despite these obstacles, the participants expressed strong aspirations for education, emphasizing dreams of pursuing specific subjects. Limited awareness of available support systems such as scholarships was noted, indicating a potential gap in accessing educational resources. Additionally, the role of government policies was raised, with some participants highlighting the need for improvements to enhance educational opportunities for child laborers. One participant mentioned:

"Mujhe yaad hai kitni mushkil thi kyunki meri family k pass zyada paisa nahi tha. Mujhe bahut kaam karna padta tha, aur is wajah se regular school jane mein mushkil hoti thi. Dikkaton

ke bawajood, meri taleem mein dilchaspi bohot strong thi. Main chahti thi ke kisi tarah ke khaas programs ya mali madad ho bachon ke liye jaise main. Peeche dekhte waqt, mujhe yeh ehsaas hota hai ke logon ko samajhna bohot zaroori hai ke kuch bachon ko kaam aur school sambhalne mein kitni mushkilat hoti hain."

One male participant mentioned,

"Mjhe parhny likhnay Ka buhaaat shok tha, barayy hokay engineer banna tha, abhii bhii dil krta hai k kuch banjaun magar halaat ijazat nahii dete, dusray bachounn Ko uniform pehnayy dekhta hun to buhaaat dil krtaa haiii k school jaaaun"

Discussion

The purpose of this study was to explore the psychological challenges faced by child labors in Pakistan. This study shed light on the complex interplay of family dynamics, past regrets, stress management, the perception of female children as liabilities, optimistic future outlooks, psychopathic tendencies, work abuse, feelings of inferiority, negative impacts on mental health, and limited access to education among child laborers. These themes provide a comprehensive understanding of the multifaceted challenges faced by children engaged in labor. The moral problem of child labor has also been tolerated by society's silence (Baland, 2000).

The narratives of the study participants illuminate the intricate dynamics of family structures, revealing how the loss of a father, remarriage, and post-marriage pressures forced them into the workforce. The common thread is the economic strain, where sole earners, often mothers, struggled to meet the family's needs. Participants, burdened with responsibilities from a young age, articulated how familial circumstances dictated their entry into the labor force. Education changes the vision of a child. It improves a child's capacity to advance. Though we couldn't afford it, it was my sincere hope and intention that my child would have a top-notch education (Mazhar, 2008). Moreover, the participants voiced regrets about missed educational opportunities due to familial obligations. Despite these regrets, a resilient optimism for the future emerged, with a collective desire to break the cycle of financial struggles and provide better prospects for their own children. If people are abruptly removed from their occupations, the household they are supporting may suffer financial consequences. (Mazhar, 2008). Stress management emerged as a crucial aspect of participants' coping mechanisms, encompassing self-reflection and seeking support. However, some participants exhibited psychopathic tendencies, engaging in self-

conversations as a response to the absence of external support structures—an alarming revelation about the mental toll of child labor. The kids labor to provide for and support their families financially.

The study unveiled societal perceptions that position female children as liabilities, leading to forced marriages within the family for financial convenience. Given that they would not talk and would be reticent about the hardship they went through, there is a chance that minors employed to labor, whether in agriculture, a workshop, or some other setting, would be abused (Fallon,1998).This underscores broader issues of gender inequality and economic constraints influencing life trajectories. Work abuse emerged as a significant challenge, with participants recounting instances of mistreatment during their labor activities. This maltreatment contributed to feelings of inferiority, especially when comparing themselves to peers who enjoyed a more conventional childhood. The trend of child maltreatment has been the most concerning part of child labor in Pakistan.

In addition to these challenges, limited access to education surfaced as a recurring theme, with participants expressing the demanding nature of their work affecting their ability to concentrate in class. The study underscored the need for increased awareness of available support systems, such as scholarships, and highlighted the role of government policies in enhancing educational opportunities for child laborers. Child labor outcomes are influenced by a number of factors, including poverty and social exclusion, labor mobility, discrimination, and inadequate social support and educational opportunities. (ILO, 2015). This study provides a comprehensive understanding of the multifaceted challenges faced by child laborers, emphasizing the need for targeted interventions that address economic vulnerabilities, gender inequalities, and mental health considerations. The findings call for concerted efforts from policymakers, educators, and society at large to break the cycles of exploitation and pave the way for a brighter future for these children. Even if child labor is eradicated in some areas or industries, it will always look for new, frequently unexpected methods to resurface (ILO,2015).

Several participants expressed regret over the missed opportunities for education due to familial responsibilities. Despite these regrets, there exists a resilient optimism for the future, with aspirations to provide better opportunities for their own children and break the cycle of financial

struggles. Many of Pakistan's rural areas, where there are no possibilities for the youth, are under feudalism. The option available to them is to use child labor in order to get some money.

The majority of children in child employment, even those who are able to attend school, find it difficult to reconcile the demands of their work and their education. They typically don't go to school full time, perform worse academically and in terms of grade advancement than their peers, and are more likely to leave school early (Child Labor Global Estimates, June 2001). The presented graphs provides a comprehensive analysis of the distribution of male and female participants based on various factors, including emotions, peer pressure, hyperactivity, conduct, and prosocial scales. The study involved a sample of five males and ten females, revealing distinct patterns in the prevalence of specific issues within each gender. Notably, males exhibited higher levels of hyperactivity, which includes extreme restlessness, fidgeting and difficulty in concentrating. While females faced greater challenges related to peer pressure which includes social skills, education competition, fear of rejection etc.

Age emerged as a crucial variable in the current study, with participants falling within the 18 to 22-year range. The findings highlighted a peak in peer pressure issues among 19-year-olds, whereas 21-year-olds demonstrated lower levels of emotional factors. This suggests an age-related variance in the experiences of participants, emphasizing the need for a nuanced understanding of developmental stages in relation to psychosocial factors. Child labor is a situation that prevents people from receiving an education, which is a violation of fundamental rights (Basu, 2001), he also highlighted how child labor is associated with lack of children rights in a country.

The threat posed by child labor is also a social issue since it arises in a specific social environment and because of a number of "social facts," as defined by Emile Durkheim, who postulated that "social facts" are the social factors that give rise to all phenomena (Edmonds, 2017). These social factors include poverty, cultural and normal issues, demand of cheap labor. Occupation-based analysis presented in the graph shed light on the distinct challenges faced by participants in different professions. Maids, comprising the majority of the sample, exhibited higher levels of hyperactivity and conduct issues, with the latter showing notable fluctuations. The consistency in prosocial factors across all occupations suggests a commonality in positive social behaviors among participants, irrespective of their professional backgrounds.

The presented findings underscore the intricate interplay of gender, age, education, and occupation with psychosocial factors. The prevalence and fluctuation of specific issues among different demographic groups emphasize the need for targeted interventions and tailored support systems. This study contributes valuable insights to the understanding of how various factors intersect to influence mental health and well-being, offering a foundation for future research and practical applications in the development of targeted interventions and support programs.

Chapter 5

Conclusions, Recommendation and Implications

Conclusion

The study concludes by exploring the complex dynamics surrounding child labor, with a particular emphasis on the familial origins of the participants, the factors that drove them to work at a young age, and the varied effects on their lives. The participants' early introduction into the workforce, financial hardships, and familial tragedies are all poignantly connected in the accounts. These people entered the workforce due to the pressure of taking care of their families, which was brought on by events like the death of a father figure or the remarriage of parents. This was frequently done at the expense of their education and upbringing. In spite of the difficulties, the participants conveyed fortitude and hope for a better future, hoping to end the cycle of misfortune for both themselves and their progeny. Additionally, the report clarifies the

child labor. The findings emphasize the need for social awareness, supportive laws, and focused interventions to break the chains of generational exploitation and argue for a comprehensive approach to address not only the economic but also the emotional and educational components of child labor.

Limitations & Recommendations

The main focus of this research was to discuss the many aspects and underlying issues associated and affected by child labor. The research paper shows some limitations that investigators should have ensured adequate amount of participants and quality control.

The fact that there were fewer male participants and more female participants might have resulted as a constraint, because more male participants had started working since the age of 9 resulting in mental health problems and burden of responsibilities so it might have been better to collect data on the basis of that.

Another limitation of the current study was that the occupation "maid" was recurring in female participants and specific domain of work is reflecting repeatedly, the data might have resulted in validity if different occupations were also brought under consideration.

Another limitation is it only looked at participants from a particular location specially households and only one city. To learn more about the effects of child labor a diverse group of people from different cities should be included.

The recommendation for future researchers is that they can go for quantitative component based on the findings of the psychosocial problems of child labor to measure the greater effects of it for better understanding.

Implications

The study's conclusions underscore the urgent requirement for comprehensive interventions that tackle the multifaceted challenges associated with child labor. By shedding light on the intricate web of family dynamics, financial struggles, and early employment initiation, the research emphasizes the crucial role of targeted support networks for families facing adversity. These insights provide a valuable resource for social activists and policymakers to formulate strategies that not only alleviate economic hardships but also prioritize the psychological well-being and educational prospects of child laborers. The implication is clear:

efforts should be directed towards fostering awareness of the detrimental impacts of child labor on long-term aspirations, self-esteem, and mental health.

These findings suggest a need for policy reforms that ensure unhindered access to education and establish safeguards against workplace abuse. The interconnected nature of family dynamics and child labor necessitates holistic approaches that consider the broader context. Stakeholders, armed with an understanding of the intricate experiences of these individuals, can collaboratively work towards breaking the cycle of exploitation. The ultimate goal is to create an environment where children can reclaim their right to a dignified and hopeful childhood. This interconnected approach aligns with the broader themes previously discussed, forming a cohesive strategy to address the multifaceted challenges faced by children engaged in labor and their families.

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Appendix A

Consent Form

نامہ اجازت

مین، ثمرہ نذیر، اپنے گروپ ممبران بشری منیر اور مریم عرفان کے ساتھ Szabist اسلام آباد سے بی ایس (سوشل سائنسز) کر رہی ہوں۔ ڈگری کی تکمیل کے لیے، ہمیں تحقیق کرنے کی ضرورت ہے۔ موجودہ تحقیق کا مقصد پاکستان میں مزدور بچوں کو درپیش نفسیاتی مشکلات کی تلاش ہے۔ اس تحقیق میں کوئی صحیح یا غلط جواب نہیں ہیں؛ یہ صرف آپ کے تجربات کے بارے میں جانے گا۔ شرکاء کی طرف سے دی گئی معلومات کو خفیہ رکھا جائے گا اور صرف تحقیقی مقاصد کے لیے استعمال کیا جائے گا۔

ذیل میں دستخط کر کے، آپ شرکت سے متعلق شرائط و ضوابط سے اتفاق کرتے ہیں۔ آپ کی توجہ کا شکریہ۔

(دستخط)

(تاریخ)

Appendix B

Demographic Sheet

1. Age: _____

2. Education: _____

3. Occupation: _____

4. Ethnic background: _____

5. Family Structure: Joint _____ Nuclear _____

6. No. of Siblings: _____

7. Marital Status:

Single _____

Married _____

Divorced _____

8. Monthly Family Income:

Appendix C

Strengths and Difficulties Questionnaire

Strengths and Difficulties Questionnaire

For each item, please mark the box for Not True, Somewhat True or Certainly True. It would help us if you answered all items as best you can even if you are not absolutely certain or the item seems daft! Please give your answers on the basis of how things have been for you over the last six months.

Your Name

Male/Female

Date of Birth.....

	Not True	Somewhat True	Certainly True
I try to be nice to other people. I care about their feelings	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I am restless, I cannot stay still for long	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I get a lot of headaches, stomach-aches or sickness	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I usually share with others (food, games, pens etc.)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I get very angry and often lose my temper	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I am usually on my own. I generally play alone or keep to myself	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I usually do as I am told	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I worry a lot	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I am helpful if someone is hurt, upset or feeling ill	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I am constantly fidgeting or squirming	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I have one good friend or more	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I fight a lot. I can make other people do what I want	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I am often unhappy, down-hearted or tearful	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Other people my age generally like me	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I am easily distracted, I find it difficult to concentrate	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I am nervous in new situations. I easily lose confidence	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I am kind to younger children	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I am often accused of lying or cheating	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Other children or young people pick on me or bully me	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I often volunteer to help others (parents, teachers, children)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I think before I do things	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I take things that are not mine from home, school or elsewhere	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I get on better with adults than with people my own age	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I have many fears, I am easily scared	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I finish the work I'm doing. My attention is good	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Your signature

Today's date

قابلیت اور مشکلات کے بارے میں سوالات

ہر اَلْتَم کے لیے، براہ کرم صحیح نہیں، کچھ حد تک سچ یا یقینی طور پر سچ کے باکس کو نشان زد کریں، اگر آپ تمام اَلْتَمز کا جواب دیتے ہیں تو یہ ہماری مدد کرے گا سب سے بہتر آپ کر سکتے ہیں یہاں تک کہ اگر آپ کو قطعی یقین نہیں ہے یا اَلْتَم ڈھیٹ لگتا ہے! براہ کرم اپنے جوابات اس بنیاد پر دیں کہ چیزیں کیسے ہیں۔

پچھلے چھ مہینوں سے آپ کے لئے رہا ہوں۔ نام _____

_____ مرد/عورت

_____ پیدائش کی تاریخ

بالکل صحیح کسی حد تک سبھی بالکل صحیح نہیں

			1- میں دوسروں کے ساتھ اچھا سلوک کرنے کی کوشش کرتا ہوں، میں ان کے جذبات کی قدر کرتا ہوں
			2- میں بے چین رہتا ہوں، میں ایک جگہ زیادہ دیر نہیں رہ سکتا
			3- میں اکثر سر درد، پیٹ درد یا بیماری کا شکار رہتا ہوں
			4- میں عام طور پر دوسروں کے ساتھ چیزیں بانٹتا ہوں جیسا کہ کھانا، کھیل، قلم وغیرہ
			5- میں بہت غصہ ہو جاتا ہوں اور اکثر اپنے سے باہر ہو جاتا ہوں

			6- میں اکثر اکیلا ہوتا ہوں، عام طور پر اکیلا ہی کہتا ہوں یا اپنے کام سے کام رکھتا ہوں
			7- میں عام طور پر وہی کرتا ہوں جو کرنے کا مجھے کہا جائے
			8- میں بہت فکر کرتا ہوں
			9- اگر کوئی تکلیف میں ہو، پریشان ہو یا برا محسوس کر رہا ہو تو میں مدد کے لئے تیار ہوتا ہوں/ مددگار ہوں
			10- میں مسلسل چڑچڑاپن اور چیخ و پکار کا شکار ہوں
			11- میرے ایک یا ایک سے زیادہ اچھے دوست ہیں
			12- میں بہت لڑتا ہوں۔ میں جو چاہوں، دوسروں سے کروا سکتا ہوں
			13- میں اکثر ناحوش، مایوس، اور رونے والا ہوتا ہوں

			14- میری عمر کے دوسرے لوگ عام طور پر مجھے پسند کرتے ہیں
			15. میری توجہ بہت آسانی سے ہٹ جاتی ہے، میرے لیے دھیان کرنا مشکل ہے
			16- میں نے حالات میں گمراہ جاتا ہوں۔ میں آسانی سے اعتماد کھو دیتا ہوں
			17- میں چھوٹے بچوں کے ساتھ خوش اخلاقی سے پیش آتا ہوں
			18- مجھ پر لوگ اکثر جھوٹ بولنے اور دھوکہ بازی کا الزام لگاتے ہیں
			19- دوسرے بچے یا نوجوان مجھے چھیڑتے ہیں یا تنگ کرتے ہیں
			20- میں اکثر رضا کارانہ طور پر دوسروں کی مدد کرتا ہوں (والدین، استاذہ، بچے)
			21- میں کچھ بھی کرنے سے پہلے سوچتا ہوں

			22. میں گھر، مدرسے یا کسی بھی جگہ سے وہ چیزیں لے لیتا ہوں جو میری نہیں ہوتی
			23. میری اپنی ہم عمر کے لوگوں کے مقابلے میں بڑوں سے زیادہ بات چیت ہے
			24. مجھے بہت سی چیزوں سے خوف آتا ہے، میں اسانی سے ڈر جاتا ہوں
			25. میں اپنا کام مکمل کرتا ہوں۔ میری توجہ اچھی ہے

آپ کے دستخط _____

آج کی تاریخ _____

Appendix D

Interview Guide

1. بچپن میں کام کرنے سے آپ کی پڑھائی پر کیا اثر پڑا؟
2. کیا اس دوران آپ کے پاس کوئی سپورٹ سسٹم یا وسائل موجود تھے؟
3. بچپن میں کام کرتے وقت آپ نے کونسے مشکلات یا پریشانیوں کا سامنا کیا؟
4. کیا آپ کو لگتا ہے کہ آپ کا موجودہ پیشہ آپ کی اور آپ کے خاندان کی ضروریات کو پورا کر سکتا ہے؟
5. کیا آپ کو لگتا ہے کہ جب دوسرے بچے کھیل رہے ہوتے تھے آپ کام میں مصروف تھے؟ اس بارے میں آپ کیا محسوس کرتے ہیں؟
6. آپ کو کیا لگتا ہے کہ آپ کا بچپن کیسا گزرا؟ کیا آپ کا بچپن باقی بچوں کی طرح گزرا ہے؟
7. کیا دوسرے بچے یا آپ کے دوست بھی کام کیا کرتے تھے یا صرف آپ ہی الگ تھے؟
8. بچپن میں کام کرنے کی وجہ سے آپ کے دوستوں اور خاندان کے ساتھ تعلقات پر کیا اثر ہوا؟
9. بچپن میں کام کرنے سے آپ کے خوابوں پر کوئی اثر پڑا؟
10. کیا بچپن کو کم عمری میں کام پر لگانا چاہیے؟ اگر ہاں یا نہیں تو کیوں؟ آپ کی رائے۔ 11. بچپن میں کام شروع کرنے کی وجہ سے آپ کی زندگی پر کیا اثرات ہوئے ہیں؟
12. کیا آپ کے پاس دوست یا خاندان والے ہیں جو آپ بھی کام میں ہاتھ بٹاتے ہیں؟
13. جب آپ غمگین یا اداس ہوتے ہیں تو کوئی ہے جسے آپ اپنے دل کی بات کر سکتے ہیں؟
14. آپ کے والدین کیا کام کرتے ہیں/ تھے؟

15. اپ اپنے خاندانی معاشی حالات کو بہتر کس طرح کرنا چاہتے ہیں/بہتر بنانے کے لئے کیا کرنا چاہتے ہیں؟